

CARIES DISEASE IN YOUNG CHILDREN

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Relevance of the topic: caries disease - among mankind is the most common disease, occurring in 93% of people. Caries is derived from the Latin word rot.

Caries is a complex, slow-moving pathological process in its hard tissues as a result of damage to tooth enamel, caused by bacteria of the oral cavity, mainly Streptococcus mutans and Streptococcus sanguis.

In general, caries disease in young children is caused by improper oral hygiene, irregular and ineffective cleaning of teeth, irrational diet, eating a lot of food rich in soft carbohydrates, low consumption of raw fruits, hypovitaminosis, lack of certain minerals (fluorine, phosphorus, calcium) in drinking water, at a young age. As a result of rickets, tuberculosis, improper formation of teeth, weakened immunity and pathology of the gastrointestinal system are considered to be one of the urgent problems of medicine today.

Purpose of work: as the purpose of the work, the occurrence, causes and spread of caries in children of kindergarten age living in the city of Urganch were studied.

Results obtained: the results of the investigation showed that children of kindergarten age had caries, and the cause of the disease was the failure to follow the rules of dental hygiene in time.

In addition to dental caries, diseases such as pulpitis, periodontitis, cysts, and fluous disease have also been identified as complications.

Conclusions: In conclusion, it can be said that the correct cleaning of teeth for the prevention of caries in children of kindergarten age - 2 times a day after meals for about 2 minutes. Mouthwash – special mouthwashes kill 99% of bacteria in the mouth. Avoid eating hot or cold foods - eating very hot or very cold foods or drinking liquids can damage tooth enamel and make it susceptible to germs. Staying under the supervision of a dentist - visiting a dentist every six months prevents yellowing of teeth, loss of mineralization, formation of gum stones and caries.

References:

1. Artikova D. O., Ruzmetova D. T. XORAZM VILOYATIDA HOMILADOR AYOLLARDA SIYDIK YO ‘LLARI INFEKSIYASINI KECHISHI VA UNGA OLIB KELUVCHI OMILLAR //INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND EDUCATION. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 1. – C. 3-4.
2. Bekchanov A. J. et al. Causes of death in infants born to women affected by Covid-19 disease //American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences (2993-2149). – 2023. – T. 1. – №. 5. – C. 34-38.
3. Khasanovich K. R., Tulibaevna R. D., Ziyaevich T. H. DISTRIBUTION OF

PERINATAL DISEASE IN NEWBORN CHILDREN IN KHORZAM PROVINCE BY CITY AND DISTRICT AND CAUSES OF DEATH //World Bulletin of Public Health. – 2021. – Т. 5. – С. 82-85.

4. Каримов Р., Аvezов М. Оценка перинатальных случаев смерти, уровня и состояния заболеваний уха, горла и носа //Журнал вестник врача. – 2021. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 60-63.

5. Karimov R. X., Tursunov X. Z., Ruzmetova D. T. Modern approaches to perinatal disease in diabetes in pregnant women //ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal. – 2021. – Т. 11. – №. 12. – С. 173-179.

6. Karimov R. X, & Musaev U. M. (2023). ANALYSIS OF RESEARCH AND COMMISSION FORENSIC EXPERTISES CONDUCTED ON LIVING PERSONS. *American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences (2993-2149)*, 1(5), 61–63. Retrieved from <http://grnjournal.us/index.php/AJPMHS/article/view/423>

7. Каримов Р. Х., Мусаев У. М., Рузметова Д. Т. ЯТРОГЕНИЯ НА ПРИМЕРАХ ИЗ ПРАКТИКИ (По данным лет обзор) //International conference on multidisciplinary science. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 10-12.

8. Каримов, Р. Х., Мусаев, У. М., Рузметова, Д. Т., & Султанов, Б. Б. (2023, October). ЯТРОГЕНИЯ В НЕОНАТОЛОГИИ (ПО ДАННЫМ ЛЕТ. ОБЗОР). In *International conference on multidisciplinary science* (Vol. 1, No. 3, pp. 76-78).

9. Каримов Р. Х. и др. ВРАЧЕБНЫЕ ОШИБКИ В ПРАКТИКЕ АКУШЕРОВ-ГИНЕКОЛОГОВ //Past and Future of Medicine: International Scientific and Practical Conference. – 2023. – Т. 2. – С. 114-117.

10. Kh K. R. et al. PATHOMORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF RESPIRATORY AIRCRAFT CHANGES IN INFANTS BORN FROM MOTHERS WITH COVID-19 //JOURNAL OF HEALTHCARE AND LIFE-SCIENCE RESEARCH. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 8. – С. 21-28.

11. Матякубова С., Рузметова Д. Особенности клинического течения при преждевременном излитии околоплодных вод и принципы ведения беременных //Журнал проблемы биологии и медицины. – 2019. – №. 1 (107). – С. 175-177.

12. Матякубова С., Рузметова Д. Фоновые факторы, влияющие на течение беременности и её исход при преждевременных разрывах плодных оболочек //Журнал проблемы биологии и медицины. – 2018. – №. 4 (104). – С. 203-205.

13. Ruzmetova D. T., Matyakubova S. A. CLINICAL PRACTICAL ASSESSMENT APPLICATION OF POLYMERASE CHAIN REACTION AS A TEST FOR ASSESSING MICROBIOCINOSIS IN PREGNANT WOMEN //Central Asian Journal of Pediatrics. – 2021. – Т. 2021. – №. 1. – С. 37-49.

14. Ruzmetova D. T., Matyakubova S. A. OCCURRENCE OF UTERINE MYOMA IN WOMEN OF REPRODUCTIVE AGE IN KHOREZM REGION //Open Access Repository. – 2023. – Т. 4. – №. 3. – С. 489-492.

15. SA M., DT R. RISK FACTORS OF DEVELOPMENT OF PRETERM PREMATURE RUPTURE OF FETAL MEMBRANES IN PREGNANT WOMEN //European Science Review. – 2018. – Т. 1.

16. Sabirjanovich Y. B. et al. ETHERIOLOGICAL FACTORS OF DEATH IN PNEUMONIAS FOUND IN NEWBORNS //EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 8. – С. 1-4.

17. Юлдашев, Б. С., Каримов, Р. Х., & Бекчанов, А. Ж. (2023, July). COVID-ўтказган оналардан туғилган чақалоқларда пневмония касаллигининг асоратлари. In *Past and Future of Medicine: International Scientific and Practical Conference* (Vol. 2, pp. 10-12).
18. Юлдашев, Б. С., Каримов, Р. Х., & Джуманиязова, Н. С. (2024). COVID-19 ЎТКАЗГАН ЧАҚАЛОҚЛАРДА ЛИМФА ТУГУНЛАРИНИНГ МОРФОЛОГИК ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ (ХОРАЗМ ВИЛОЯТИ ПАТОЛОГИК АНАТОМИЯ ЭКСПЕРТИЗА БЮРОСИ, ХОРАЗМ ВИЛОЯТ ПЕРИНАТАЛ МАРКАЗИ). *Молодые ученые*, 2(3), 15-16.
19. Каримов Р.Х. / ХОРАЗМ ВИЛОЯТИДА ПЕРИНАТАЛ ЎЛИМНИНГСАБАБЛАРИ ВА ПАТОЛОГИК АНАТОМИЯСИ // Автореферат: - Т: "Muxarririyat va nashriyot" бўлими, 2021 – 46 б.
20. Каримов Р.Х. / ХОРАЗМ ВИЛОЯТИДА ПЕРИНАТАЛ ЎЛИМНИНГСАБАБЛАРИ ВА ПАТОЛОГИК АНАТОМИЯСИ // Диссертация: - Т: "Muxarririyat va nashriyot" бўлими, 2021 – 111 б.
21. Tulibayevna R. D. Characteristics of Urogenital Tract Microbiota During Pregnancy // *Research Journal of Trauma and Disability Studies*. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 10. – С. 249-254.
22. Юлдашев, Б. С., Каримов, Р. Х., & Джуманиязова, Н. С. (2024). ПАНДЕМИЯ ДАВРИДА ПНЕВМОНИЯ КАСАЛЛИГИ БИЛАН КАСАЛЛАНГАН ЧАҚАЛОҚЛАРДА ЛИМФА ТУГУНЛАРИНИНГ МОРФОЛОГИК ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ ЎЛИМ САБАБЛАРИ. *AMALIY VA TIBBIYOT FANLARI ILMIY JURNALI*, 3(1), 197-201.
23. Юлдашев Б. С., Каримов Р. Х., Бекчанов А. Ж. COVID-19 ЎТКАЗГАН ЧАҚАЛОҚЛАРДА ПНЕВМОНИЯНИНГ МОРФОЛОГИК ХУСУСИЯТИ // *International Scientific and Practical Conference of Students and Young Scientists" Sustainable Development: Problems, Analysis, Prospects"* (Poland). – 2023. – С. 26-28.
24. Yuldashev V. S. et al. Causes of Pneumonia In Infants Born of Mothers Infected With Covid-19 // *International Journal of Integrative and Modern Medicine*. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 9-16.
25. Yuldashev, V. S., Kuruyazov, A. Q., Khodzhimuratov, O., & Karimov, R. X. (2023). OCCURRENCE OF CLINICAL PALATE AND LIP DEFECT WITH FACIAL ANOMALIES IN KHORAZM REGION. *International Bulletin of Medical Sciences and Clinical Research*, 3(11), 80-85.
26. Kuruyazov Akbar Quranbaevich, Karimov Rasulbek Khasanovich, Ruzmetova Dilfuza Tulibaevna, & Bobojanov Yoldoshboy Bakhtiyor o'g'li. (2024). PREVENTION OF PERIODONTITIS DISEASE IN MIDDLE-AGED WOMEN. *INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON MEDICINE, SCIENCE, AND EDUCATION*, 1(1), 271–274. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10599587>
27. Yuldashev, V. S., Kuruyazov, A. Q., Khodzhimuratov, O., & Karimov, R. X. (2023). A CASE OF LIP DEFECT WITH FACIAL ANOMALIES IN KHORAZM REGION. *American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences* (2993-2149), 1(9), 547-552.
28. Sabirjanevich, Y. B., Khasanovich, K. R., Tulibaevna, R. D., & Safarboevich, R. S. (2024). RATE OF GLAUCOMA IN PENSION AGE CITIZENS (2023 in the example of the city of Urganch). *International Journal of Alternative and Contemporary Therapy*, 2(1), 4-7.
29. Sabirjanevich, Y. B., Khasanovich, K. R., & Safarboevich, R. S. (2024). RELATIONSHIP OF OTHER TYPES OF DISEASES WITH EYE DISEASES. *МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА*, 2(1), 29-35.